

Operational Challenges and Solution Approaches for Low Voltage Distribution Grids - A Review

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Abstract

To facilitate the energy transition towards a decarbonized energy sector, distribution system operators will have to address several challenges by upgrading and redesigning the operation of the distribution grid. This review paper presents an overview of the operational challenges of low voltage distribution grids (LVDGs) operating under a high penetration of photovoltaic systems (PVs) and electric vehicles (EVs). Specifically, the impacts of PVs and EVs on the voltage profile, net-demand profile and network congestion, as well as network asymmetry are demonstrated and discussed. This is achieved by utilizing real measurements from LVDGs in the Cyprus power system and by examining different case studies that consider future operating conditions. A detailed review of management solutions available in the literature for active LVDGs is then presented that aim to mitigate the detrimental impacts of PVs and EVs. These include wired solutions such as on-line-tap changing transformers, reactive power control by smart inverters, active power control through PV curtailments, energy storage systems, EV charging strategies, and phase balancing schemes. In addition, several management solutions are implemented to representative LV feeders, which have been made publicly available, where their effectiveness and potential areas of improvement are evaluated.

Keywords: Active power control, battery storage, congestion management, electric vehicles, low voltage distribution grid, phase balancing, photovoltaic system, reactive power control, voltage regulation.

1. Introduction

Towards the target of net zero emissions by 2050 (Paris climate Agreement [1]), various governments have placed policies and subsidies [2] that aim to promote low-carbon technologies with the focus mainly on residential photovoltaic (PV) systems, energy storage, and the adoption of electric vehicles (EV). As a result, the PV [3] and EV [4] industries have experienced an exponential growth over the last decade, as seen in Fig. 1(a)-(b), which is expected to continue in the foreseeable future. The recent global energy market disruptions have forced countries, especially in the European Union (EU), to reduce their dependency on natural gas and other fossil fuels. To avoid energy shortages and soaring electricity prices, supporting schemes such as the REPowerEU

Figure 1: (a) PV capacity [3] and (b) number of EVs [4], and (c) projected additions of rooftop PVs [3].

plan [5] in the EU and the Inflation Reduction Act [6] in the USA have been implemented. As a result, the transition towards green technologies is accelerating at a global scale.

In 2022, the global installations of new PVs increased by 45% compared to 2021, reaching 240 GW, of which 118 GW were new rooftop solar installations [3]. The rapid growth of rooftop PVs is expected to continue in the coming years. Figure 1(c) illustrates the projection of yearly new installations of rooftop PVs until 2027, with an estimated 268 GW of new capacity installations per year. Moreover, with the current growth rates of PVs, it is anticipated that by 2026 the global installed solar capacity will surpass that of natural gas, and by 2027 it will exceed the capacity of coal [7]. This marks a significant milestone towards a decarbonized energy sector. Similar encouraging trends are observed for the penetration of EVs. In 2022, 10 million EVs were sold, marking a 55% increase compared to 2021 and bringing the total number of EVs to 26 million [4]. The strong growth of EVs is also reflected in the increasing sales share of EVs, which refers to the proportion of EVs sold relative to the total new vehicle sales in a year. The EV sales share increased from 4% to 14% in 2022 and in 2023 it reached 18%. However, to align with the net-zero emissions target, the EV sales share must reach 65% by 2030.

Besides their beneficial effects, PVs and EVs can also pose several challenges. The increasing intermittent solar generation, the growing demand for EV charging, and consumer-oriented products to maximize economic benefits through energy storage systems increase the operational complexity of LVDGs. A large penetration of PVs and EVs in LVDGs may introduce several operational challenges and power quality concerns [8–10] including: frequent violations of voltage and thermal limits, grid congestion, intense asymmetric loading conditions, and an intermittent and low-inertia power generation. Recognizing the critical role of LVDGs in the energy transition, this review article conducts an in-depth investigation of their operation under high penetrations of PVs and EVs.

The majority of relevant articles [11–21] focuses on a particular low-carbon technology and its impacts on the distribution grid, rather than considering the combined impacts of multiple technologies. Specifically, in [11], the authors mainly examine the impact of high PV penetrations on the voltage profile of residential LVDGs; however, mitigating solutions are not presented. The authors in [12, 13] present solutions only for voltage regulation with the aim to enhance the PV hosting capacity, including PV inverter control, low voltage regulators, network reconfiguration,

and battery storage systems (BSS). Commercially available as well as emerging technologies for voltage regulation and voltage unbalance mitigation are presented in [14] for distribution grids with high penetrations of distributed energy resources (DER). A survey of voltage control approaches for mitigating the voltage rise in PV rich LVDGs is presented in [15] with particular focus in the use of energy storage systems, active and reactive power control of PV inverters, on load tap change (OLTC) transformers, and network reconfiguration; however, other solution approaches for congestion and network asymmetry are not considered. The impact of the voltage regulation on the distribution network is analytically presented in [16]. Ancillary services oriented for distribution grids are presented in [17] for managing the detrimental impacts of DERs, including voltage regulation, voltage unbalance mitigation, congestion management, and power smoothing. The impacts of EVs on the distribution grid such as under-voltage conditions, harmonic distortions, equipment overloading, and increase of power losses are presented in [18]. Similarly, in [19] the impacts on the distribution grid of different EV charging strategies are evaluated. To facilitate higher EV penetrations, vehicle-to-grid services are presented in [20] with a discussion of the benefits and challenges towards their implementation. A novel model based on a non-stationary Markov chain is presented in [21] that considers the uncertainties related to the integration of EVs. This approach allows to capture the dynamic behavior of EVs more accurately, enabling more representative case studies. Additionally, in [22] the authors present novel static models of inverter-based generation for accurate load flow and fault analysis; however, this work is limited to microgrids and only PVs are considered. The main features, infrastructure, protection framework, and objectives of energy management in smart grids are discussed in [23]; however, the challenges and solution approaches related to low-carbon technologies are not analyzed.

Limited relevant review works have consider multiple low-carbon technologies. The impacts of distributed installations of PV plants and wind farms in terms of voltage, power losses, and electricity cost are investigated in [24]; however this study considers a MV distribution grid with an industrial load profile. In [25], an extensive overview of DER control and management strategies is provided; however, the focus of the paper is mainly on the practical challenges towards their implementation with a limited discussion on the overall impacts of low-carbon technologies. A survey of machine learning and deep learning models used in various applications for the energy conversion, forecasting, and power prediction of wind, solar, and hydro-based generation is presented in [26]; however, this survey does not consider any aspects of grid management. The steady-state challenges associated with the variability, uncertainty, and inflexibility of wind and solar energy are reviewed in [27], with a focus on voltage profile degradation, increased power losses, increased stress on infrastructure assets, and bidirectional power flows; however, this study does not explore any management solutions to address the aforementioned challenges. Similarly, the challenges posed by variable wind and solar generation, along with mitigation technologies, are discussed in [28]; however, the authors primarily focus on transmission and primary distribution grids, without addressing the impacts and solution technologies related to EVs. In [29] an assessment framework to maximize the hosting capacity of PVs and EVs of an entire city is presented by leveraging their synergies; however, this study does not present the overall challenges of LVDGs

and does not consider any other assets. The individual as well as combined impact of PVs and EVs on grid stability, power quality, and energy economics are presented in [30]. Interestingly, it is reported in [30] that the coordinated operation of PVs and EVs can negate their individual detrimental impacts, highlighting the need of advanced control strategies in LVDGs; however, other solution approaches are not adequately analyzed. A probabilistic assessment of the impact of several low-carbon technologies, including PVs and EVs, based on a Monte Carlo approach is presented in [31]; however, the investigation is limited to voltage and congestion issues and it does not explore any potential management solutions.

This review article aims to further fill this gap by providing a comprehensive overview of the overall LVDG challenges related to multiple low-carbon technologies. Furthermore, a holistic overview of management solutions to facilitate the modernization of the LVDG and to address the PV and EV related challenges is also provided. Selected solutions that are already in use or are deemed applicable in the near future (require limited infrastructure upgrades) are implemented in representative low voltage (LV) feeders and their effectiveness is evaluated in a comparative analysis. Table 1 provides a content summary of the related works, including this paper for comparison purposes. While other works may focus on specific challenges or management solutions, this paper provides a comprehensive analysis of key challenges related to multiple low-carbon technologies. These challenges include over-voltage, under-voltage, congestion and overloading due to reverse power flow and EV charging demand, as well as network and load asymmetries. Moreover, a review of possible solution approaches and a comparative evaluation of various solutions is also provided, including infrastructure upgrade and reactive power control for voltage management, active power control of PVs, BSS, and EVs for both congestion and voltage management, and phase balancing strategies to symmetrize the grid operation. Additionally, in contrast to other works, this paper utilizes representative LV feeders that have been developed and made publicly available. Through these feeders, the impact of various challenges on the LVDG operation and the effectiveness of selected management solutions is demonstrated via realistic practical examples. The single-line diagram and a brief description of each LV feeder is given in the Appendix, while their complete documentation can be found in the provided link¹. In summary, the contributions of this review article are:

1. Analysis of the impact and challenges caused by high PV and EV penetration in LVDGs considering (i) voltage violations; (ii) grid congestion and thermal limit violations; (iii) increase of asymmetric operation.
2. Overview of solutions for distribution grids, to address the above challenges, with emphasis on (i) infrastructure upgrade and reactive control for voltage management; (ii) active power control of PVs, energy storage systems, and EV chargers to manage congestion and the grid voltage; (iii) phase balancing strategies to symmetrize the grid operation.
3. A set of representative European LV feeders, including urban, sub-urban, and rural grids, have been developed with the aid of Electricity Authority of Cyprus, that is the Cyprus distri-

¹<https://www.kios.ucy.ac.cy/LVtestsystems>

bution system operator (DSO). These synthesized feeders have been designed to replicate the key features of each network type, enabling the production of high-quality research results. The LV feeders are used to demonstrate the key challenges of modern LVDGs and to perform a comparative evaluation of the effectiveness of various solutions. Additionally, the simulation models for the LV feeders as well as the models of various low-carbon technologies (PV, BSS, EV) with different operating modes, developed in OpenDSS and MATLAB/Simulink, have been made publicly available¹ to support further research activities.

Table 1: Content Summary of Related Works

Ref.	Low-Carbon Technologies	LVDG Challenges	Solution Approaches	Practical Examples	Considered Network
[11]	PVs	Over-voltage	N/A	Challenges	Sub-urban feeder
[12]	PVs	Partially	Increase hosting capacity	N/A	N/A
[13]	PVs, EVs	Over-voltage Under-voltage	Reactive power, curtail., BSS ^a , smart EV charg.	N/A	N/A
[14]	PVs	Over-voltage, voltage unbalance	OLTC, reactive power, BSS, converter topolog.	N/A	N/A
[15]	PVs	N/A	OLTC, reactive power, curtail., BSS	N/A	N/A
[16]	PVs	Over-voltage	OLTC, reactive power, curtailment	Challenges	IEEE 34-Node MV distr. system
[17]	N/A	N/A	OLTC, reactive power, curtail., BSS, DSM ^b	N/A	N/A
[18]	EVs	Under-voltage, harmonics, overloading, losses	Smart EV charg., V2G ^c	N/A	N/A
[19]	EVs	Financial impacts	Different Smart EV charg. schemes	Solution	MV distr. grid
[20]	EVs	N/A	V2G Services	N/A	N/A
[21]	EVs	N/A	Improved EV behavior model	Solution	N/A
[24]	PVs, Wind	Voltage, losses electricity cost	N/A	Challenges	MV distr. grid
[25]	PVs, EVs	N/A	Broad overview of DER control schemes	N/A	N/A
[27]	PVs, Wind	Over-voltage, losses, overloading, reverse power flow	N/A	From the literature	N/A
[28]	PVs, Wind	Transm. & MV grids: Power quality, power flow, stability	Overview of central. and distr. techn.	N/A	N/A
[29]	PVs, EVs	N/A	Increase hosting capacity, PV-EV synergies	Solution	MV/LV network
[30]	PVs, EVs	Voltage, stability, power quality, enery economics	Increase hosting capacity, PV-EV synergies	From the literature	N/A
[31]	PVs, EVs heat pumbs	Voltage, congestion	N/A	Challenges	LV feeders
This paper	PVs, EVs	Voltage, congestion and overloading, network asymmetry	OLTC, reactive power, curtail., BSS, smart EV charg., phase balancing	Challenges and Solutions	Urban, Sub-urban, and Rural LV Feeders

^aBattery Storage System, ^bDemand-Side Management, ^cVehicle-to-grid

The structure of the paper is as follows. In section 2, the impact of PVs and EVs on the voltage profile and solutions for voltage management through wired solutions and reactive power control are presented. Section 3 considers the impact of PVs and EVs on the net-demand profile, along with solutions for congestion management through active power control. The impact of PVs and EVs on the network asymmetry and solutions for phase balancing are presented in section 4, followed by a discussion in section 5. Finally, the paper concludes in section 6.

2. Wired Solutions and Reactive Power Control for Voltage Related Challenges

This section discusses the impact of a high penetration of PVs and EVs on the grid's voltage profile, which can cause significant challenges related to voltage limit violations. Furthermore, different solutions for effective voltage management are reviewed and evaluated. Specifically, the voltage management approaches covered in this section include wired solutions through on line tap changing (OLTC) transformers and non-wired solutions through reactive power control (RPC) by smart inverters. Note that hereafter, the urban, sub-urban, and rural feeders refer to the developed representative LV feeders that have been made publicly available.

2.1. Impact of PVs and EVs on the Voltage Profile

The increasing PV installation and EV charging demand are changing the operating conditions and the voltage profile of LVDGs. Expression (1) shows how the voltage in adjacent nodes, n and $n - 1$, in a radial feeder is affected by the power flow along the distribution line that connects them when assuming insignificant coupling between phases [13, 32],

$$V_n = V_{n-1} - \frac{R_{n,n-1} (P_n^L - P_n^g) + X_{n,n-1} (Q_n^L - Q_n^g)}{V_{n-1}} \quad (1)$$

where P_n^L and Q_n^L are the total active and reactive power of loads at node n , P_n^g and Q_n^g the total active and reactive power by distributed energy resources (DER) at node n , $R_{n,n-1}$ and $X_{n,n-1}$ are the resistance and inductive reactance of the considered line, and V_n , V_{n-1} are the voltage magnitude at nodes n and $n - 1$. Equation (1) shows that the impact of the active/reactive power flow on the voltage profile is scaled by the line parameters. Typical lines in LVDGs have high resistance to reactance R/X ratio, 4-6 times higher compared to transmission systems, and therefore both active and reactive power can significantly affect the voltage profile.

Figure 2 illustrates the voltage profile as a function of the distance from the secondary substation (SS) as well as the voltage variation at the end-of-feeder (EoF) for the three types of residential LV feeders. The operation of each LV feeder has been investigated over a 24-hour period, taking into account representative load profiles under current loading conditions. Figure 2(a) illustrates the daily average voltage at various distances from the SS, while Fig. 2(b) presents the voltage variability of each feeder within a day. In general, rural systems have a higher grid impedance compared to urban and sub-urban systems and therefore their voltage profile is more sensitive to the loading conditions. Under significant penetrations of PVs and EVs, urban systems are expected to face challenges primarily related to congestion and overloading due to high population

Figure 2: (a) Voltage profile and (b) voltage variation of different types of LVDGs, present-day loading conditions.

Figure 3: (a) Current and expected net load profile and (b) resulting voltage profile at the EoF, sub-urban system.

density and low grid impedance. Conversely, in sub-urban and rural systems, the main limiting factor for high PV and EV penetrations will be their impact on the voltage profile.

As indicated by (1), during reverse power flow the voltage within the LVDG increases in relation to the secondary substation and under high PV penetration it could exceed admissible limits [11, 13, 14]. In contrast, the extra energy demand for EV charging during the evening and night hours increases the forward power flow, resulting in a greater voltage drop within the LVDG. The impact of a high penetration of PVs and EVs on the LVDG voltage profile is illustrated in Fig. 3. Specifically, Fig. 3(a) depicts a typical, present-day load profile for a residential sub-urban feeder with 50 consumers, as well as an expected future load profile under significant penetration of PVs and EVs. In the expected future load profile, it is assumed that each household is equipped with a 3 kWp PV system and that 15 households have an EV with a 50 kWh battery capacity and a Level 2 – 240 V, 16 A charger. Figure 3(b) illustrates the impact on the LVDG voltage profile under future load conditions compared to the current situation. Specifically, Fig. 3(b) shows the voltage rise that can occur during peak PV generation and the excess voltage drop during the EV charging hours. These contradictory impacts lead to an intense increase in daily voltage variation, which could be challenging to manage with only conventional measures such as the seasonal off-load tap change of the distribution transformer.

2.2. Solutions for Voltage Management

By analyzing (1), four types of effective voltage management solutions can be identified: i) reduction of resistance R and reactance X of the distribution lines, ii) voltage management at the secondary substation, iii) reactive power support and iv) active power management. To determine

Figure 4: OLTC transformer for: (a) managing the substation voltage and (b) regulating the end-of-feeder voltage.

the effectiveness of each solution, the following metric is introduced,

$$V_O^{max} = \max \{V_i - \bar{V}\} \quad (2)$$

where V_O^{max} is a metric for the maximum over-voltage limit violation of the entire LVDG under examination. The \bar{V} corresponds to the maximum voltage limit (253 V), as defined by most grid regulations, and index i corresponds to the i -th node voltage of the LVDG. In section 2.2.1, wired solutions which include a distribution line upgrade, different schemes for OLTC transformers, and solid-state transformers are reviewed for voltage management. In addition, voltage regulation strategies based on reactive power provision by smart inverters are discussed in section 2.2.2.

2.2.1. Wired Solutions - Infrastructure Upgrade

To improve the voltage profile of the LVDG the distribution lines should have low resistive R and inductive X values. This network-side solution requires an infrastructure upgrade in which existing conductors are replaced with conductors of larger cross-sectional area to reduce the impedance of the line. While effective, logistics and high costs restrict the applicability of this network-side solution to grid expansions or when new infrastructure is developed.

Due to its proven effective operation in primary substations, OLTC transformers are increasingly being considered for secondary substations that have high penetration of DERs [33, 34]. Figure 4 shows two conventional operational schemes of an OLTC transformer. The OLTC in Fig. 4(a) is used to regulate the voltage at its terminal within a dead-band of the specified set point. To avoid any unnecessary tap changes, a time delay of 10-120 s is introduced before triggering the tap changing mechanism [35]. Instead of regulating the terminal voltage, the line drop compensation in Fig. 4(b) regulates the voltage at the end of the feeder, which is considered as the critical node. This scheme is very effective when there is only one MV feeder or when several feeders have similar load behaviours. However, when the OLTC transformer supplies power to several feeders with different load behaviours, then the line drop compensation scheme cannot ensure that all critical nodes will be within acceptable voltage limits.

The impact of the OLTC operation mode illustrated in Fig. 4(a) is depicted in Fig. 5, considering the sub-urban system with a 1.025 p.u target voltage at its terminals, a 0.015 p.u dead-band and ± 0.0125 p.u per tap change. Specifically, Fig. 5(a) shows the daily voltage variation considering an off-line tap change transformer with a constant tap setting, which is a common practice in LVDGs. In this operation, the daily voltage variation, induced by the PV generation at noon

Figure 5: End of feeder voltage of sub-urban system with 50 PV systems (75% penetration) and 10 EVs with: (a) offline tap change transformer and (b) OLTC transformer.

Figure 6: Voltage at secondary substations: (a) Near the start, and (b) near the end of the MV grid.

and by the increased demand during the evening and night hours, is more than 55 V (0.24 p.u.). Consequently, since the daily voltage variation is more than 0.2 p.u., there is no single tap setting that can satisfy both voltage limits. Figure 5(b) shows how an OLTC transformer can maintain the voltage variation within 0.2 p.u., ensuring that the voltage operational limits are satisfied.

Most related works on the literature focus in the coordination between the OLTC transformer and other controllable assets such as smart inverters and energy storage systems [36–38]. Their aim is to minimize the OLTC tap changes and its subsequent mechanical degradation while simultaneously providing an effective voltage regulation across the distribution grid. While very effective in managing the grid voltage, the OLTC transformer cannot have a system wide deployment in LVDGs due to high costs. Instead, grid monitoring can be utilized to identify secondary substations that experience intense daily voltage variations where non-wire solutions may be incapable in preventing voltage violations. The daily voltage variation of a LVDG is affected by (i) its internal loads and (ii) by the voltage of the higher level MV grid. Depending on the location of the secondary substation in relation to the MV grid and its overall DERs penetration, the voltage variation of the LVDG can change significantly. Figure 6 shows the voltage at two secondary substations in Cyprus for one week during summer. The first secondary substation is located near the primary transformer of an MV grid with limited penetration of DERs, while the second is located near the end of a large MV grid with moderate penetration of DERs. The impact of the relative location of the LVDG within the MV grid and its DER penetration is shown by the significantly higher voltage variation in Fig. 6(b). In this case, non-wire solutions may be insufficient and therefore the upgrade of the distribution transformer to an OLTC can be conducted in a targeted approach by utilizing a grid monitoring analysis.

In contrast to traditional transformers, solid-state transformers (SST) utilize state-of-the-art power electronics [39] instead of a magnetic core to adjust voltage levels. An SST can provide reactive power support and harmonic filtering to improve the power quality, offers superior controllability over active and reactive power flow, and it has improved voltage regulation capabilities [40, 41]. An SST typically consists of three stages: the MV stage with an AC-DC rectifier, the isolation stage with a DC-DC converter, and the LV stage with a DC-AC inverter [42]. Compared to traditional transformers, SSTs are more compact, with a reduced size and weight per kVA. Moreover, SSTs can interconnect systems operating at different voltages or frequencies. However, the most significant advantage of SSTs is their capability to facilitate hybrid AC-DC systems.

The low voltage DC link within the SST topology can be used to establish a common DC bus for PVs, EVs, energy storage systems, and electronic-based loads. Since these technologies have key components that are DC in nature, a hybrid AC-DC LVDG allows for more efficient and straightforward integration by eliminating the need for DC-AC conversion [43]. Furthermore, DC LVDGs can enable power flow control in meshed networks through the use of controllable converters and since they are decoupled by the AC grid, they also remain largely unaffected by external voltage or frequency disturbances [44]. Despite these advantages, DC LVDGs face several challenges, including high initial costs, a lack of market-ready components, and limited standardization and regulation, with applications currently limited to pilot projects. Similarly, while SSTs have high potential, they also face several limitations, such as higher costs, lower efficiency, and reduced robustness and reliability compared to traditional transformers [42]. Implementing SSTs also requires complex control systems and a redesign of protection schemes, further complicating their adoption.

2.2.2. Reactive Power Control by Smart Inverters

Based on the IEEE 1547-2018, DERs are required to actively participate in voltage regulation. For this reason, distribution system operators (DSO) are specifying in their national grid codes that PV inverters connected to LVDGs must provide RPC for voltage regulation [45]. Most RPC schemes followed by DSOs include constant power factor and droop-based control of reactive power with either power factor/Watt, power factor/Watt-Volt or Var/Volt modes [46].

Under the current regulations, the provision of reactive power from DERs is assumed to have a zero cost. However, three sources of cost associated with the requirement and provision of RPC can be identified as (i) the additional cost due to oversized inverters since the provision of adequate reactive power requires extra capacity for the inverter, increasing the capital investment; (ii) the cost due to increased grid losses since reactive power increases the current magnitude and the thermal losses; (iii) the cost associated with the inverter lifetime degradation since the provision of reactive power by the inverter increases the thermal stress, reducing its lifetime and increasing the maintenance/replacement cost [47]. Therefore, monetary incentives through an appropriate pricing in an ancillary services market framework that fairly compensate the prosumers for their loss of inverter lifetime may be needed to ensure the viability of RPC. In this direction, accurate thermal models that describe the long-term inverter lifetime degradation in relation with reactive

power provision can be used to establish a basis for the cost of RPC [48].

In the literature, RPC schemes are presented which aim to minimize the reactive power needed for voltage regulation. These methods can be categorized into local, centralized, or distributed methods. In local control methods [46, 49–53], a smart inverter utilizes information that is available locally to determine the amount of reactive power that a PV should inject/absorb without requiring information from other parts of the system. In [50] an RPC scheme is presented that uses the information of the grid parameters to negate the voltage rise induced by PVs. The reactive power capabilities of smart inverters and additional shunt reactors are utilized in [51] to mitigate overvoltage conditions in secondary networks. Historical measurements are exploited in [53] to generate optimal Watt/Var droop-curves for each individual inverter. This approach optimizes the overall deployment of reactive power and avoids situations where the inverters near the secondary substation are under-utilized. A centralized control framework [54–57], requires a centralized controller that has full knowledge of the entire system and is responsible for the decision making. The centralized controller receives information from all PV inverters regarding their voltage, generation, and available capacity. Then, based on the desired objectives, the centralized controller calculates and transmits back to each smart inverter an optimal set point for reactive power deployment. For instance, in [55] PV inverters are utilized in a multi-objective optimal power flow framework to reduce network losses, improve the voltage profile, and minimize curtailments. An RPC scheme is presented in [56] which is based on model predictive control that utilizes a linearized network model and is therefore applicable in real-time. In [57], the PV inverters operate in the power factor/Watt-Volt mode until the critical node exhibits over-voltage conditions. At this instance, the inverters closer to the end receive a command from the centralized controller to absorb maximum reactive power. In a distributed control framework [58–60], the decision making is distributed to several control nodes across the system. Each control node is responsible for its local assets and shares some information with other control nodes to achieve an overall coordinated and optimal operation. Compared to a centralized control framework, a distributed method is more scalable and has a higher resiliency to faults. However, a distributed method has a higher complexity and the coordination of the different control units can be challenging.

While centralized schemes show promising results due to better network observability, they generally require a two-way communication infrastructure, and they operate in an optimization framework that, in most cases, requires heavy computations and knowledge of the grid model. Such infrastructure is currently not widely adopted in LVDCs which restricts for the time being the system-wide applicability of centralized RPC methods. However, with continuous advancements and the eventual mass adoption of new communication technologies such as 5G, the applicability of centralized schemes will increase significantly. Therefore, this study considers the following local and centralized RPC modes in the sub-urban system: (i) no RPC, $pf = 1$; (ii) constant power factor, $pf = 0.9$; (iii) $\cos\phi(P)$ - power factor/Watt control [46]; (iv) $\cos\phi(P, V)$ - power factor/Watt-Volt control [46]; (v) $Q(V)$ - Var/Volt control [46]; (vi) RPC based on optimal power flow - OPF [55]; (vii) constant Var, Fix- Q , $Q = P_{PV}\tan(\cos^{-1}(0.9))$. Note that the considered schemes are either rule-based, resulting in minimal computational burden, or they follow a cen-

Figure 7: Settings of local RPC modes: (a) $\cos\phi(P)$, (b) $Q(V)$, and (c) $\cos\phi(P, V)$.

Figure 8: (a) Reactive power deployment and (b) resulting EoF voltage in Scenario A, sub-urban system.

tralized approach leveraging convex optimization. On a personal computer with 8 GB RAM and an Intel Core-i7 3.2 GHz processor, the centralized method has an average execution time of 0.15 s, demonstrating its suitability for real-time applications.

The settings of the local modes $\cos\phi(P)$, $\cos\phi(P, V)$, and $Q(V)$ are illustrated in Fig. 7. The settings of the remaining local methods, $pf = 0.9$ and Fix- Q , are not shown due to their simplicity. The considered centralized RPC scheme is based on a simplified version of [55] where the objective function of the optimal power flow framework is to minimize the deployment of reactive power for voltage management. The operation of the above RPC modes is investigated under two scenarios. **Scenario A - Intense variation of the source voltage:** It is assumed that the secondary substation is located near the end of an MV grid with a high PV penetration. This increases the risk of over-voltage conditions within the LVDG as its source voltage during the PV generation hours will be higher than normal due to a voltage rise propagating from the MV grid.

Scenario B - Mild variation of the source voltage: The secondary substation is assumed to be near the beginning of an MV grid with moderate distributed generation. Therefore, in this scenario the source voltage during the PV generation hours will experience a lower voltage-rise.

Note that in both scenarios all households in the sub-urban LVDG are equipped with a PV system; 3 kWp for single-phase and 5 kWp for three-phase consumers. Figure 8 shows the total provision of reactive power from the PV inverters and the corresponding grid voltage at the EoF for scenario A, where it can be seen that in the case of $pf = 1$ (no RPC) there are voltage

Figure 9: (a) Reactive power deployment and (b) resulting EoF voltage in Scenario B, sub-urban system.

Table 2: Comparison Between Different RPC Methods

Sc.	KPI	pf=1	pf=0.9	$\cos\phi(P)$	$\cos\phi(P, V)$	$Q(V)$	OPF	Fix- Q
A	V_O^{max} [V]	4.65	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Q_e [kVarh]	0	637	480	353	493	99	917
	E_L [kWh]	39	59	54	49	52	42	73
B	V_O^{max} [V]	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Q_e [kVarh]	0	637	480	105	120	0	917
	E_L [kWh]	40	62	56	42	44	40	77

violations. Note that the active power profile of the considered PVs corresponds to a sunny day in August in Cyprus [8]. In Table 2, the impact of each mode on over-voltage mitigation V_O^{max} , amount of reactive energy absorbed Q_e , and total energy losses E_L is listed for both scenarios. In scenario A, all RPC modes manage to prevent the overvoltage conditions that appear when no RPC is considered. However, because of the provision of reactive power for voltage support all RPC modes result in an increase of grid losses. The local RPC modes utilize significantly higher reactive power and consequently they increase the grid losses by 25-87%, with the voltage dependent modes $\cos\phi(P, V)$ and $Q(V)$ introducing the least additional energy losses. It must be noted that all local modes in this scenario seem to have a similar performance. This is because the maximum grid voltage is reached during noon in which all local RPC modes are absorbing Q_{max} to maintain the voltage within the admissible upper limit. In comparison, the centralized OPF RPC mode introduces only a 7% increase in the grid losses as the deployment of reactive power is optimally determined. In addition, the centralized RPC mode deploys the least amount of reactive power which reduces the loading on distribution lines/transformers, in comparison with the local modes. However, the considered centralized RPC mode over-utilizes the inverters near the EoF as the reactive power from these inverters has the highest impact on the critical node. Frequent high utilization of the inverters near the EoF for voltage management can eventually lead to a reduced lifetime for these inverters [47, 48]. Additionally, since there is no compensation for reactive power provision, this practise can impose an unfair replacement cost on the affected prosumers.

In the case that the voltage rise within the LVDG without RPC is not sufficient to cause violations, the local voltage dependent, and centralized RPC modes can maintain the PV inverters close to a unity power factor, thus avoiding overcompensation. This is considered in scenario B and is illustrated in Fig. 9(b) where the grid voltage although high is still within the limits. In this scenario, only the $\cos\phi(P, V)$ and $Q(V)$ modes have a reduced provision of reactive power

compared to other local modes, while the centralized RPC mode completely avoids the deployment of reactive power, see Fig. 9(a). Consequently, as given in Table 2, under scenario B these modes have significantly lower grid losses.

It must be mentioned that most RPC schemes are based on (1) which assumes that the phases are decoupled. Under this assumption, the power flow in phase i does not have a significant impact on the voltage of phase j , with $i, j = [a, b, c]$. The particularities of LVDGs however render this assumption invalid. Due to the inductive [61] and neutral coupling [62], the operation of single-phase inverters connected to phase i will also have a significant impact on the voltage of a different phase. The phase coupling that exists in four-wire LVDGs can reduce the effectiveness of RPC schemes that are based on (1) [63]. However, this coupling also presents an opportunity to develop RPC schemes that not only coordinate upstream and downstream inverters but also enable resource sharing between phases for unconventional voltage regulation [58, 64, 65].

3. Active Power Control to Address Congestion and Voltage Related Challenges

This section discusses the impact of a high penetration of PVs and EVs on the grid's loading conditions and possible solutions for congestion management through active power control. Given that typical lines in LVDGs have high resistance to reactance R/X ratio, active power control can also be utilized for voltage management which is also discussed in this section. Specifically, the active power control approaches and their impact on the grid congestion and voltage profile that are included in this section are (i) PV curtailment, (ii) energy storage systems, and (iii) demand side management through EV charging strategies. Note that the wired solution of an infrastructure upgrade, which can also be used for increasing the network capacity, is not discussed further due to its significant costs.

3.1. Impact of PVs and EVs on the Net-Demand

A major challenge when having high penetration of PVs in distribution grids is the reverse power flow that can occur due to low consumption of the residential load during the peak PV generation hours. Several studies [8, 31, 66, 67] have indicated that during intense reverse power flow, see Fig. 2(a), the lines near the secondary substation as well as the distribution transformer might exceed their thermal limits. In addition, solar generation can have a detrimental impact on the frequency stability of the entire system. With an increasing inverter-based and inertia-free generation by both commercial and residential PV systems, conventional generating units might temporarily be taken out of service [9, 68]. Consequently, the power system's overall inertia level is reduced. A reduced inertia can render the power system more vulnerable and sensitive to power imbalances [69, 70]. Another challenge is the high ramp-up of demand, as shown in Fig. 2(a), which occurs in the afternoon by the simultaneous reduction of the PV output and the increase of demand. Under high PV penetrations the ramp-up requirement can exceed the capabilities of the committed conventional generation units. Commonly, these operational challenges are within the responsibilities of the transmission system operator. However, with the increasing share of

residential PV systems it is essential that the DSO can also contribute to mitigate these challenges at the LVDG level.

Equally challenging will be the task to manage the extra energy demand for EV charging as indicated in Fig. 2(a). Considering that most EVs will be privately owned and that the commercial EV charging infrastructure is underdeveloped, most users will plug-in their vehicles after the work hours at their home chargers. Consequently, the peak demand from feeders with high EV integration will grow significantly and could exceed the thermal limits of the distribution transformer and lines/cables near the secondary substation [10, 31, 71]. Furthermore, the grid operator may also impose export/import limits to ensure the integrity of the overall distribution network [72]. To ensure compliance with these limits, avoid congestion, and maintain sufficient system inertia and ramp-up capabilities under high penetrations of PVs and EVs, active power control at the LVDG level is required.

3.2. Solutions for Congestion and Voltage Management

Section 3.2 outlines strategies for active power control designed to mitigate congestion, prevent equipment overloading, reduce reverse power flow, and improve the voltage profile in LVDGs. The strategies include (i) PV curtailment, (ii) the utilization of energy storage systems, and (iii) demand-side management through smart charging of EVs.

3.2.1. PV Curtailment

The term PV curtailment refers to the override of the inverters' maximum power point tracking [73] functionality to a lower value. The motivation for PV curtailment is threefold. First, it can be used to prevent over-generation conditions where the generation needed by the committed conventional units is less than their minimum generation limit [68] and to maintain sufficient ramp-up capabilities. Second, high penetration of PVs can lead to intense reverse power flows within the distribution grid that can create congestion issues at primary and secondary transformers and at the lines at the beginning of the feeder [31], which can be prevented with PV curtailment. Third, due to the high R/X ratio in LVDGs, PV curtailment is an effective method for regulating the grid voltage with however an associated cost to the prosumers.

The increase of PV installations coupled with inadequate investments in developing the grid infrastructure can lead to an increase of curtailments. In April 2022, Spanish authorities had to curtail the generation of PV plants for the first time due to excessive surplus energy. In Cyprus, during the first four months of 2023 the daily average curtailment reached 21%, while the yearly average was 14% [74]. The average curtailed renewable energy in California, USA, increased from 308 GWh in 2016 to 2450 GWh in 2022 [75]. Similarly, in Australia the PV curtailments increased from 54 GWh in 2017 to over 2000 GWh in 2021 [76] with a further 40% increase in 2022. The aforementioned curtailment statistics refer to the total system curtailments which consist of the curtailments by large commercial PV installations as well as by small-scale residential PV systems. Specifically for residential systems, in the Netherlands during the first six months of 2023 the PV curtailments of residential PV systems tripled compared with the same time period

in 2022. However, curtailments create uncertainty over the economic viability of PV investments and therefore can create set backs in their future growth. For this reason, the solution of PV curtailment must be seen as an intermediate measure to maintain network integrity until the necessary solutions, such as energy storage and grid reinforcements, are in place. In this direction, China over the last decade has been making significant investments in expanding its power grid infrastructure [77]. As a result, the curtailment of renewable energy sources in China reduced from 16% in 2012 to 3% in 2022 [76].

Curtailment methods can be divided to static and dynamic techniques according to how the curtailment P_c (PV generation limit) is defined [13]. In static methods, the generation limit P_C is set to a predefined value, which can be determined either locally or remotely by the DSO through ripple control functionality. This limit is implemented to prevent over-generation or congestion conditions. With the increasing PV penetration in LVDGs, DSOs are mandating that residential PV systems be equipped with the technical capability for remote-controlled output reduction [78]. This reduction is typically specified as a percentage of the installed PV capacity. In addition to ripple control, the DSO may impose export limits, which can be either fixed or flexible, to manage the power fed into the grid by residential PV systems. In [79], the overall curtailment of the aggregated PV output of the entire power system is determined through a day-ahead unit commitment scheduling to prevent over-generation conditions and to maintain enough flexibility for system stability. Then, the curtailment requirements of each region of the power system are determined via short-term weather forecasts to minimize PV generation fluctuations.

In dynamic methods [80–85], P_C is calculated based on the operating conditions and the considered network constraints. These methods are mainly utilized for preventing over-voltage and congestion conditions in the distribution grid. Volt/Watt droop curves are commonly employed to reduce PV output during over-voltage conditions, while sensitivity-based optimization frameworks are used to minimize the overall PV curtailments for grid management. However, both approaches tend to disproportionately affect PV inverters located near the EoF, where voltages are typically highest. This results in unfair curtailments, as prosumers near the EoF face excessive curtailment, while those closer to the substation experience minimal reductions in production [85]. To address this issue, fairness-aware methods have been developed, introducing novel PV curtailment strategies that either require communication between the PV inverters [82, 83], operate using local information only [84], or are solved in a distributed fashion [85]. To increase the fairness of PV curtailments, it is essential to first establish the desired metric for evaluation. In general, there are three main approaches for enhancing PV curtailment fairness [83]: (i) maximizing and proportionally equally distributing financial benefits (ii) minimizing the proportionally equal PV curtailment based on the maximum available PV power of each household, and (iii) maximizing and equalizing energy exports according to each household’s maximum possible energy export. While each of these approaches is fair within the context of its specific metric, if judged by other metrics they might appear unfair. From the aforementioned approaches, maximizing energy exports is particularly beneficial for households with high self-consumption. These households have marginal impact on the grid and by maximizing their energy export, their unfair curtailment is

Figure 10: Considered settings of a local droop-based PV curtailment.

Figure 11: (a) Total PV generation and (b) EoF grid voltage with over-voltage conditions, sub-urban system.

avoided. However, while fairness-aware methods effectively eliminate locational penalties by not favouring the prosumers near the head of the feeder, they often result in higher overall energy curtailment compared to fairness-agnostic methods. Moreover, multi-objective methods can be formulated by combining several metrics into a single-objective function using the weighted sum method [86]. This approach enables a more comprehensive and complex evaluation of fairness by considering multiple metrics simultaneously. However, determining appropriate weights for each objective function can be challenging. These weights influence the trade-offs between different metrics, impacting the overall fairness of the solution. Despite its effectiveness in preventing over-voltages, active power curtailment for voltage management is avoided to keep as high as possible the penetration of renewable resources. In most cases, PV curtailment is used in coordination with other solutions and is deployed as a last resource for voltage management [55, 81–84]. Nonetheless, to illustrate the impact of active power curtailment the following local (static P_c and Volt/Watt droop scheme) and centralized (OPF-based) techniques are considered for the sub-urban system: (i) static curtailment with $P_c = [1, 0.8, 0.6, 0.4]$ p.u.; (ii) Volt/Watt $P_c = f(V)$, droop-based scheme shown in Fig. 10 [80, 83]; (iii) optimal power flow (OPF) based curtailment [83].

The objective function of the centralized OPF-based curtailment scheme is to minimize the total curtailed energy needed for voltage management. The impact of each PV curtailment method is investigated considering a scenario where the RPC is insufficient in preventing over-voltage conditions when applied to the sub-urban system. Table 3 contains the peak reverse power flow, amount of curtailed energy as well as the percentage of curtailed energy in relation with the total PV generation for all PV curtailment schemes. Furthermore, Fig. 11(a) illustrates the total PV generation while Fig. 11(b) shows the EoF grid voltage under the different PV curtailment schemes. In terms of congestion management, a lower upper limit P_c for the static method results to a lower peak reverse power flow P_R in the expense of significantly higher curtailed energy. Specifically, the financial loss is up to 45% for the prosumers when $P_c = 0.4$ p.u. is deployed. The local droop-based and OPF-based curtailment schemes are deployed only during over-voltage conditions and therefore

Table 3: Active Power Curtailment - KPIs

Curtail. Method	Rev. Power P_R (kW)	Curt. Energy (kWh)	Norm. Curt. Energy (%)
$P_c = 1$	-101	0	0
$P_c = 0.8$	-86	119	9
$P_c = 0.6$	-54	329	25
$P_c = 0.4$	-22	601	45
$P_c = f(v)$	-82	126	9
<i>OPF</i>	-85	65	5

have the least amount of curtailed energy at 126 kWh and 65 kWh respectively. Therefore, their impact on congestion management can be limited, as indicated in Table 3.

In terms of voltage management, the local-based and OPF-based schemes manage to efficiently prevent the over-voltage conditions. In contrast, the static method requires a significant amount of curtailed energy to restrict the voltage within the limits with $P_c = 0.6$ p.u., which results to 329 kWh of energy loss. However, it must be mentioned that in the static method the associated cost is fairly distributed amongst all prosumers. In the considered dynamic methods a prosumer near the EoF has 8 to 10 times higher amount of curtailed energy in comparison with a prosumer near the substation. Furthermore, in case the grid voltage is with the limits, then the dynamic method will not curtail any amount of energy while the static curtailment method will impose the same curtailment unnecessarily.

3.2.2. Energy Storage

Battery storage systems (BSS) offer significant advantages for grid operators by effectively managing surplus energy during peak PV generation periods. They improve the voltage profile, reduce congestion, and prevent the need for PV curtailments. Additionally, BSS can provide ancillary services, such as frequency response, mitigate PV related voltage fluctuations caused by cloud movement, and delay expensive grid upgrades [87]. For LV prosumers, BSS can reduce electricity costs and are typically operated in self-consumption (SC) mode. In this mode, prosumers are encouraged through various schemes, such as net-metering and net-billing [88], to maximize the consumption of their generated energy. Figure 12 shows the concept of a BSS operating in a self-consumption mode, where the BSS charging is initiated when there is a net export of energy [89]. Given that typical BSS used in residential installations have relatively small capacity, generally ranging from 4 to 8 kWh, this charging scheme often results to the BSS being fully charged before the peak PV generation period [90].

Several works aimed to address this issue and to provide several additional services. The relevant works are divided to centralized [54, 91–94], distributed [32, 95, 96] and local control methods [89, 97–100]. Additionally, BSSs in LVDGs can be utilized for (i) peak shaving applications for enabling higher PV and EV penetrations without requiring expensive infrastructure upgrades [91], (ii) power smoothing applications for mitigating the PV output fluctuations [100], (iii) voltage management through rule-based control frameworks [32, 89, 93, 95–99] or optimization frameworks [54, 94], (iv) electricity cost minimization considering variable pricing schemes [54], and

Figure 12: The concept of the self-consumption battery mode.

(v) maximizing energy arbitrage at either household or feeder level [92]. For instance, in [54] the electricity cost of prosumers and the cost of grid losses are minimized while maintaining the grid regulations using distributed BSSs. In [93], utility owned BSSs are utilized in a centralized control scheme based on a sensitivity analysis for voltage regulation by taking into consideration the fair usage of all BSSs. A distributed control strategy is presented in [32] for voltage management that incorporates a local droop-based control for the initial dispatch of the BSSs and a secondary distributed consensus-based control for fair and efficient utilization of the available BSS capacity. In [95], using linear programming and voltage sensitivity indices the optimal PV output for initiating BSS charging is derived in a decentralized framework as to limit over-voltages and the reverse power flow. A local controller is used in [96] to regulate the state of charge of each BSS while a consensus based distributed controller coordinates the BSSs for an effective voltage regulation. Several local static control strategies are assessed in [89, 99], both from a technical as well as from an economical point of view. Following a different approach, in [91] and [100] strategies based on model predictive control are presented. Note that the inherent characteristics of a centralized, distributed, and local-based control framework discussed in section 2.2.2 are broadly applicable across various relevant applications, including the aforementioned BSS coordination schemes.

Centralized or distributed methods are usually based on optimization schemes where BSS are represented by mathematical models. The power losses of BSS are modeled as either a piece-wise linear [54] or quadratic loss functions [101] and require non-convex constraints resulting to non-convex optimization problems which are challenging to solve [102]. Typically, these problems are solved through convex relaxations of the BSS power loss constraints resulting in computationally efficient formulations. Another approach that can be adopted for the coordination of PV and BSS in distribution grids are the operating envelopes [72, 103, 104]. In this approach, the DSO determines time-varying export/import limits (operating envelopes) at the PCC of individual prosumers. The export/import limits are usually derived in an AC-OPF framework and are sent to third-party aggregators. A common assumption is that if the intended operation of the aggregators is within the defined operating envelopes, then grid issues will not occur. However, due to the neutral coupling in LVDGs, voltage violations can still occur [64]. In this case, if all prosumers operate at their defined maximum import/export values, the voltage is expected to reach its limit. Consequently, if just one prosumer operates below its defined maximum import/export limit, the power deviation

Table 5: Active Power Management – Battery Storage System

BSS Charg. Mode	E_L (kWh)	E_R (kWh)	P_R^{max} (kW)	V_O^{max} (V)
No BSS	66	670	116	4.61
SC - $\bar{P}_{ch} = 1, T_d = 0h$	60	617	116	4.61
SC - $\bar{P}_{ch} = 0.5, T_d = 3h$	59	617	99	1.98
BSS - [95]	59	617	104	2.77
BSS - [89]	57	617	102	2.16

Figure 14: (a) Charging/discharging power of a 1-ph BSS, (b) house consumption with BSS, (c) total active power at the secondary substation (SS) and (d) BSS PoC voltage.

reverse power flow is detected the charging of the BSS is initiated.

Figure 14(a) illustrates the operation of a single BSS for the different charging schemes and Fig. 14(b) the resulting household consumption. Furthermore, Fig. 14(c) illustrates the impact of all BSSs on the net power flow at the secondary substation. Due to the relatively small BSS capacity, under the conventional charging scheme the BSSs are fully charged before noon. The various charging settings for the conventional SC scheme, as well as those in [89] and [95], limit the initial dispatch of the BSS to ensure that there is available capacity during the peak PV generation. Despite a low penetration of BSS, the peak reverse power flow P_R^{max} is reduced by more than 10%. Additionally, the reverse energy E_R that flows into the MVDG is reduced from 670 kWh to 617 kWh. Reducing peak reverse power flow can prevent local congestion and over-generation conditions, and thus avoiding PV curtailments. Moreover, in Table 5, it is indicated that with a modest number of BSS the grid losses E_L can be reduced up to 14%. In general, a BSS can reduce the reverse as well as the forward power flow, and therefore it can be utilized for both congestion and/or voltage management. Note that if not properly tuned, the local-based coordination schemes may lead to the under-utilization of the BSS (due to delay or charging restrictions) which can increase the electricity cost of the prosumers compared to the conventional SC scheme. Furthermore, Fig. 14 also illustrates the difficulty of extracting the full potential of BSS through local-based control schemes for improving the grid operation. The considered local-based coordination schemes while they improve the grid operation, their impact can be marginal. As these schemes operate by utilizing information that is only available locally, their overall operation

Figure 15: (a) Transformer loading and (b) positive sequence voltage at EoF for urban and rural systems under normal charging and 30% EV penetration.

is most often sub-optimal in terms of grid management. Additionally, BSS coordination schemes that respond to pricing signals with an objective function to maximize energy arbitrage [92] can lead to grid congestion, when the electricity price is low and BSS penetration is significant. To fully leverage the capabilities of BSS, advanced control schemes based on centralized or distributed frameworks that utilize global system information are more suitable despite their drawback of having a higher complexity and a higher implementation cost.

Battery storage systems are widely regarded as a key solution to the challenges that distribution grids face in accommodating high penetrations of PVs and EVs. This is evident from the extensive literature that utilizes BSS to enhance and optimize the distribution grid operation. However, fully realizing the potential of this technology presents significant challenges [106]. Effective integration of BSS into the distribution grid requires the development of information and communication technologies at the end-user level, their real-time management requires complex and advanced control systems, and it requires the establishment of new regulatory frameworks to enable their deployment.

3.2.3. Demand-side management – EV charging strategies

A high penetration of EV chargers at households, which mainly have a single-phase connection, imposes several challenges in the operation of the LVDG [10, 19, 107]. Figure 15 shows the loading on the transformer and the EoF positive-sequence voltage for the urban and rural system with 30% EV penetration with uncontrollable charging. Due to their low resistive cables and high energy density, urban systems are expected to primarily face congestion related problems. In contrast, the voltage in rural systems is more sensitive to changes of active power and under high EV penetration rural systems will face mainly under-voltage conditions.

Demand-side management (DSM) is an effective strategy for reducing peak loads, avoiding grid congestion, and lower electricity costs by decreasing reliance on fossil fuels. An EV can be leveraged as a controllable load with flexible electricity demand, enabling unidirectional DSM functionalities such as congestion management, valley filling and flattening of peak demands through load shifting [108–113]. In general, DSM strategies can be categorized into economic and technological approaches [114]. Economic-based DSM approaches rely on financial incentives to encourage load shifting during periods of high energy demand, such as a lower electricity price during off-peak periods. The most widely adopted economic-based DSM approach is the time-of-use (ToU) tariff, where electricity prices vary depending on the time of the day, with higher prices during peak

demand periods [115]. The impact of a ToU tariff for an indirect EV charging management is investigated in [116]. The study revealed that under high EV penetrations, an economic-based DSM can inadvertently create a second peak during lower-priced intervals, highlighting the need for a more direct DSM approach. Instead of a ToU tariff, real time electricity pricing based on wholesale market rates can be used. In this approach, electricity costs are communicated in advance to the consumers, allowing them to react and adjust their consumption accordingly [117].

In technological DSM approaches, the controllable assets are managed directly to ensure the desired objectives in a smart grid framework. In this context and to alleviate their detrimental impacts and facilitate a high penetration of EVs in distribution grids, several methodologies have been proposed for their coordinated charging. For instance, in [111] by considering the randomness of the EV time of arrival, departure time and a minimum amount of energy that must be charged, a distributed charging strategy is presented that minimizes the peak-to-average ratio of the aggregated demand. Two control strategies are presented in [112] which are based on a genetic algorithm that minimize the daily cost of the EV aggregator and its peak demand. However, charging strategies that are based on real-time pricing of electricity can lead to high charging demands when there is high penetration of wind and solar energy due to a cheaper electricity price [19]. A centralized strategy that can mitigate both thermal and voltage violations in LV feeders is presented in [113]. This strategy monitors the available capacity on the lines/transformer as well as if there are any under-voltage conditions in the presence of EV charging. On such occasion, a suitable number of EVs that must disconnect is calculated giving priority to EVs that have low state-of-charge.

An EV can also operate as a controllable generation source, enabling its use in bidirectional vehicle-to-grid (V2G) services [118]. This capability allows the EV to draw as well as supply power to the grid, enhancing its operation. The energy storage capacity of EVs can be utilized to support the grid by reducing peak loads and by providing ancillary services such as frequency support, voltage management, and load balancing. Specifically, in [119] charging and discharging strategies for EVs using V2G-enabled chargers are presented, taking into account the uncertainties of PV production, EV demand, and household consumption. The resulting EV charging/discharging operation significantly reduces both the peak-valley difference and overall load variation. A closed-loop hierarchical V2G framework is presented in [120] which enables EVs to provide supplementary frequency regulation when demanded by the control center. This method is demonstrated to be capable of significantly reducing frequency fluctuations, while ensuring that the expected SoC of participating EVs is achieved. Similarly, in [121] a distributed coordination scheme for EVs is proposed to enable their participation in frequency regulation while fulfilling their daily mobility energy requirements. An on-board bidirectional charger that enables EVs to provide V2G reactive power support for voltage management is presented in [122]. In [123], three-phase four-wire balancing PV inverters and EV chargers are utilized to symmetrize the network by transferring power from high loaded to light loaded phases. Similarly, a game theoretic approach for load balancing is presented in [124] by deriving the charging profile of each EV to reduce the overall system phase imbalance.

Figure 16: EV charging scheme considering available transformer capacity.

To incentivize the EV owners to offer grid support functionalities, a bilateral trading mechanism is proposed in [125] where EV owners can sell ancillary services to EV aggregators. Other transactive methods for coordinating the charging of EVs have been proposed in [126, 127], however these methods require a market-based infrastructure which currently is not widely adopted in distribution grids. In general, the coordination of EV charging is achieved through optimization schemes based either on mathematical modeling or heuristic approaches with the aim to either (i) minimize grid losses, (ii) minimize the total cost of energy, or (iii) maximize the economic benefits of EV aggregators/owners [128]. The coordinated charging of EVs is usually scheduled based on the network conditions considering the electricity cost of the EV owners. However, as the main purpose of the EV is the mobility of its user, monetary incentives are secondary to the user's expectations of having sufficient driving range after a charging period. Aspects of user satisfaction such as the desired SoC at the time of departure, charging urgency when plugged-in, time needed to achieve a full charge, and a minimum SoC after a specific charging time are in most cases neglected. In this direction, EV charging strategies that consider different aspects of user preferences criteria are presented in [129–131]. Furthermore, most methodologies consider only one part of the distribution grid [132], i.e., only the MV or LV network. Therefore, the inter-dependencies of these networks are neglected and while the network integrity is ensured for the considered part of the distribution grid, the unaccounted part might still be subject to voltage and congestion issues. In [129, 131, 133], EV charging methods are presented for integrated MV/LV networks, thus ensuring the network integrity of the whole distribution grid.

To examine the impact of EV charging strategies on the LVDG operation the following charging schemes are applied and compared in the urban system: (i) normal, uncontrollable charging; (ii) smart charging, Fig. 16, a simplified version of [113].

In the smart charging mode, each plugged-in EV (EV_i) sends a charging demand (Cd_i) signal along with its current SoC_i to the centralized controller. The centralized controller receives information about the loading of the transformer (S_t) and calculates the total number of vehicles (k) that the feeder can supply. If this number is lower than the total number (m) of EVs requesting charging, then a charging signal (Cs_i) is sent only to the k vehicles with the lowest SoC. In the following scenario, there are in total 60 EVs, which correspond to a 30% EV penetration. In addition, the nominal capacity of the transformer is 400 kVA.

Figure 17(a) illustrates the impact of the two charging modes on transformer loading where a significant violation of the transformer loading limit can be observed in the normal mode. Utilizing

Figure 17: (a) Power at the SS and (b) EV charging considering normal and smart charging modes, urban LVDG.

the flexible EV demand, the smart mode avoids congestion by shifting the excess charging load to later night hours where more capacity is available. Figure 17(b) shows the charging process of an EV under the normal and smart charging modes. In the normal mode, charging continues uninterrupted until either the departure time or until the SoC reaches 100%. In the smart mode, the centralized controller coordinates the EV charging to ensure network integrity by interrupting the charging of selected EVs, which resume charging when network capacity is available. This practical approach reduces the peak-to-average index from 1.79 under the uncontrollable charging to 1.35 and it completely prevents over-loading conditions.

Despite the promising results, EV charging strategies face several technical challenges and social barriers [10, 20]. A major concern is the willingness of EV owners to participate in such schemes. With a lacking commercial charging infrastructure most EV owners will prefer to charge their cars at their convenience. In addition, bidirectional vehicle-to-grid services require additional charging cycles by the EV batteries which are a known contributor to their degradation [134]. To increase the public’s acceptance and the willingness of EV owners to participate in smart charging strategies it is important to create for them new revenue streams and to quantify the exact impact these strategies will have on their EVs. Pricing schemes and compensation strategies for EV owners based on accurate and prognostic battery degradation models [135] are therefore needed to reduce the EV owners’ concerns regarding their vehicle’s life cycle.

3.2.4. End-User Participation in Electricity Markets

Liberated electricity markets are characterized by free competition, where numerous participants can engage as monopolistic structures are abolished. End-users equipped with PV systems, BSS, and EVs, have the potential to participate in these markets by offering flexibility and generation capacity. However, the purchasing and bidding impact of individual end-users is insignificant to the overall needs of the power system, effectively limiting their direct market participation. This limitation can be overcome through the involvement of aggregators or by the formation of local energy communities.

Aggregators are typically third-party entities responsible for the collective management of multiple end-users’ assets [136]. By aggregating these resources, the aggregator can participate in electricity markets as a single, more substantial entity, thereby creating economic value by enabling end-users’ assets to provide services at scale. These services can include selling aggregated power to wholesale markets, providing upward/downward flexibility in balancing markets, and

offering ancillary services such as frequency reserves [137]. In emerging electricity markets that enable congestion management services [138], the aggregator’s main goal is to maximize financial returns while considering model-free network constraints, such as the loading on distribution transformers to avoid congestion and violation of its thermal limits. However, in most countries, local grid issues such as increased network asymmetry and voltage violations may still persist because addressing these issues requires a detailed network model, which is often not available to aggregators, and are not yet managed through a market-based approach.

Similarly, local energy communities are formed when end-users collectively own and operate assets with significant capacity [139], such as PV plants and BSS, at a feeder level. The local energy community framework facilitates participation in local energy markets for balancing demand and supply, in peer-to-peer energy trading to minimize grid exchanges, and forming virtual power plants that act as single entities, enabling their effective participation in electricity markets [140] while ensuring the integrity of the local grid. Beyond cost savings and additional revenue generation, energy communities promote energy independence and sustainability, as a significant portion of their energy needs is met through local, low-carbon technologies.

4. Phase Balancing Solutions to Address Grid Asymmetry Related Challenges

This sections discusses the impact of a high penetration of PVs and EVs on the grid’s loading asymmetry, the associated increase of neutral and zero-sequence currents, and the resulting induced neutral voltage and its effect on the voltage unbalance factor (VUF). Furthermore, phase balancing solutions for network symmetrization are reviewed including (i) wired solutions through phase selectors and (ii) non-wired solutions through advanced inverter control strategies.

4.1. Impact of PVs and EVs on Network Asymmetry

An LVDG mainly supplies with electricity single-phase connected consumers where, in most cases, the number of consumers connected to each supply phase is not equal. Moreover, loads in three-phase connected consumers are usually unevenly connected to each phase. As a result, the current composition in LVDGs is asymmetrical and can have significant percentage of negative and zero sequence components [8] which reduce the power quality. In particular, the negative sequence component, in addition to the LVDG, can also affect the medium voltage distribution grid and the transmission system, while the zero sequence component is restricted within the LVDG due to the widely used D-Y distribution transformers. Therefore, the effects of the zero sequence component and the resulting neutral current exist mainly at the LVDG level. Specifically, the zero sequence can deteriorate the power quality [141, 142] and can cause violation of the LVDG operational limits due to the increased neutral current. In Fig. 18(a), measurements of the neutral current from four SS in Cyprus are illustrated in percentage of the three line currents. These measurements demonstrate that even with existing conventional loading conditions the neutral current is high and in the range of 10-40% of the load current, indicating a significant loading asymmetry.

Residential PV systems and EV chargers typically have the same phase connection as their corresponding household. The resulting unequal distribution of PV capacity and EV charging

Figure 18: Neutral current: (a) measurement at SS, percentage of line currents, (b) beginning of feeder (BoF) under current and future load profile conditions. (c) Neutral voltage and (d) voltage unbalance factor at EoF, sub-urban system

demand across the supply phases can increase the loading asymmetry, neutral current, and voltage violations within the LVDG, which can limit its hosting capacity [143]. From Fig. 18(b) the increase of the loading asymmetry due to the asymmetrical integration of PV generation and EV charging demand is evident during the future conditions by the sharp increase of the neutral current during the noon hours (peak PV generation) and late afternoon hours (peak EV charging demand) respectively. To save costs, in some networks the neutral conductor has a smaller diameter compared to the phase wires. The increase of the neutral current due to the highly asymmetrical PV generation and EV charging demand can therefore overload the neutral wire [66].

Additionally, a high current flow through the neutral conductor creates a non-negligible voltage drop across it, as shown in Fig. 18(c), especially under future load profile conditions. A non-negligible neutral voltage affects all consumers, as given by (3) [144],

$$V_{pn} = \sqrt{V_p^2 + V_n^2 - 2V_pV_n \cos(\theta_p - \theta_n)} \quad (3)$$

where V_p and V_n are the phase voltage and neutral voltage magnitude respectively, and θ_p and θ_n are the phase angle and neutral angle correspondingly, for each phase $p = [a, b, c]$. Equation (3) shows how a non-negligible neutral voltage can have a severe impact on the voltage magnitudes [62] V_{pn} and on the voltage asymmetry depending on the $\cos(\theta_p - \theta_n)$ term. The impact of the neutral voltage on the voltage asymmetry is highlighted in Fig. 18(d). In this figure, the VUF, which is one of the key power quality indices, is illustrated for current and future load conditions and is calculated according to the sequence voltage component as [145],

$$VUF = \frac{\sqrt{V_0^2 + V_2^2}}{V_1} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

where V_0 , V_1 and V_2 are the magnitudes of the zero, positive and negative voltage sequence respectively. It should be noted that the definition for the VUF (4) used in this paper differs from the

IEC definition which only considers the positive and negative sequence components. In three-phase four-wire networks there is a significant zero-sequence component which if neglected can lead to wrong perceptions of the unbalance factor. From Fig. 18(d) it can be seen that an asymmetrical penetration of PVs and EVs can increase the VUF beyond the regulations limit of 2% considering 10-minute average RMS values [146]. Therefore, to maintain satisfactory power quality, increase the LVDG hosting capacity for PVs and EVs, and to prevent violations of thermal and voltage limits, strategies for phase balancing are needed.

4.2. Solutions for Phase Balancing

The increasing penetration of PVs and EVs in LVDGs can also increase the network asymmetry, especially in cases where the PV inverters and EV chargers are single-phase connected. Due to the aforementioned detrimental impacts of an excessive unbalanced operation and strict grid codes, several works have been proposed for phase balancing.

The relevant literature for phase balancing can be divided in wired [145, 147–150] and non-wired solutions [123, 124, 151–155]. In the first category, phase selectors are utilized for re-configuring the connection of single-phase consumers, PV/BSS inverters and EV chargers according to the loading conditions. For instance, in [145] a centralized controller receives periodically measurements from smart meters regarding the consumption of each house. Then, based on the total loading of each phase it determines optimally which loads should change a supply phase to balance the network. For LVDGs without smart meters, a phase balancing scheme is presented in [147] that utilizes only measurable data from phase selectors. Following a similar approach, in [148, 149] the connection of single-phase EV chargers and PV inverters is optimally determined to reduce the network asymmetry, improve the voltage profile and reduce grid losses. Besides phase selectors, shunt active power filters can also be utilized to compensate harmonics as well as the negative and zero sequence current [150]. While wired solutions are effective in balancing the network, they introduce an additional cost for the phase-selectors and active power filters. In addition, to prevent rapid degradation of the phase selector, its operation is limited which reduces its effectiveness.

Non-wired solutions are based in control strategies for three-phase PV/BSS inverters and EV chargers. To reduce the negative sequence, centralized compensation schemes that utilize 3-ph 3-wire inverters are presented in [151, 152] at a building and in [153] at a substation level. A decentralized control scheme capable of reducing the negative sequence component as well as mitigate harmonic distortions of a distribution feeder is presented in [154]. For compensating the zero-sequence current, 3-ph 4-wire inverters are needed. In [123], such inverters are used for balancing the network as they can inject unbalanced power according to the loading conditions. Moreover, 3-ph 4-wire inverters are capable of drawing power from one or more phases and transfer it to the rest with the purpose of symmetrizing the load current. However, phase balancing with zero-sequence compensation capabilities requires three-phase four-leg inverters [156, 157] which are not favorable due to higher costs. In a different direction, in [124] and [155] phase balancing schemes based on load/generation shifting by delaying the charging of EVs to time slots with light load conditions or by an optimal operation of the BSS are presented respectively.

Figure 19: Phase balancing scheme utilizing 3-ph, 4-wire PV inverters.

To examine the impact of phase balancing schemes in the operation of the LVDG, a simplified version of [123] is applied to the 3-ph 4-wire PV inverters of the sub-urban system as illustrated in Fig. 19. In essence, the 3-ph inverters are drawing power from the supply phases that are below the mean power P_m to inject it to the supply phases that are exceeding it with $\Delta P_a^t + \Delta P_b^t + \Delta P_c^t = 0$. This is done with respect to the capacity limit of each inverter, giving priority to the PV generated power. In Fig. 20, the VUF (4) is illustrated for each 3-ph system node. Under normal operation, the voltage asymmetry near the EoF (bus node 70) is close to the operational limit of 2%, as shown in Fig. 20(a). The balancing scheme manages to reduce the peak VUF from 1.8% to 0.9%, Fig. 20(b), which is significantly lower than the admissible limit. In addition, Fig. 21 illustrates the current unbalance factor (CUF) at the beginning of the feeder as well as a phase-neutral and phase-ground voltage near the EoF. Note that the CUF is calculated similarly as the VUF (4). The phase balancing scheme significantly reduces the current asymmetry as the CUF is mostly below 5%. In addition, by symmetrizing the load current the neutral displacement is minimized and as a result the phase-neutral voltage is similar to the phase-ground voltage, black dash line Fig. 21(b). In general, this improves the voltage profile and voltage violations can be avoided.

While effective in symmetrizing the network, 3-ph 4-wire inverters are not common in LVDGs as they are more expensive due to the extra switching elements. Given the benefits it is important to improve the network and voltage asymmetry by utilizing the widely adopted single-phase and 3-ph 3-wire inverters. The coordination of single-phase storage systems and demand-response schemes in targeted consumers can aid in symmetrizing the network. In addition, it is possible to use single-phase inverters to form distributed wye and delta connected compensators [158]. This approach allows to use single-phase inverters to compensate both the negative and zero sequence voltage component with the drawback of requiring specific phase connections.

5. Discussion

A lot of effort and resources are needed for upgrading the distribution grid to accommodate the expected surge of PVs and EVs and to facilitate the energy transition. To limit the investments for network reinforcements, smart and non-wired solutions are required for optimal utilization of the available flexibility. By implementing grid management solutions that utilize intelligent

Figure 20: Voltage unbalance factor across the LVDG (a) normal, (b) with phase balancing, sub-urban system.

Figure 21: (a) Current unbalance factor at BoF and (b) voltage at EoF.

technologies, such as reactive power control, PV curtailments, energy storage systems, demand-side management for smart EV charging, and phase balancing, costly infrastructure upgrades can be delayed or reduced. Furthermore, holistic control and management strategies that coordinate all assets (PV, BSS, EV, OLTC, home energy platforms) will be the next step when the appropriate infrastructure is in place. The definition of appropriate incentives and pricing schemes that consider asset degradation (smart inverters, BSS, and EVs) will aid in the wider acceptance of the proposed management solutions. With large-scale deployment of the presented solutions providing ancillary services, LVDGs will have significant flexibility. For its efficient and optimal utilization, as well as to increase system reliability, coordination between the different grid operators is required [159]. By collaborating and sharing resources, grid operators can enhance the overall reliability of the power system and can avoid contradictory actions.

Technological advancements of inverters will also increase the available flexibility by providing additional grid support functionalities, such as virtual inertia. To enable two-way communication between different assets as well as to support and handle the data exchange from smart meters/devices and advanced metering infrastructures (AMI), information and communication technologies will have a vital role in the modern distribution grid. However, with the digitalisation of the power system it is critical to ensure that its cyber network is adequately secure. A vulnerable cyber network can be exploited in a malicious attacks with the purpose of damaging or limiting the operation of the physical network. As a result, cyber-security is an important aspect [160] of a modern LVDG. In addition, the AMI and smart meters/devices will generate a vast amount of data. Machine learning based tools will utilize this development to provide a better understanding of the LVDG operation as well as to power new applications. For instance, short-term forecasts of

the local demand [161] and renewable generation [162] will be made readily available. Based on these forecasts, DSOs can proactively take actions to avoid imbalances, enhancing system stability under high intermittent generation.

6. Conclusions

Low voltage distribution grids have an essential role in the energy transition to low-carbon technologies. However, while these technologies offer numerous benefits, the high penetration of PVs and EVs presents significant challenges for DSOs. This paper highlighted these challenges in practical examples by analyzing real-world measurements and by conducting case studies in representative test feeders, which have been made publicly available. Specifically, the study focused on the impact of PVs and EVs on the (i) voltage profile with severe violations of the regulation limits, (ii) congestion and overloading of transformers due to an intense reverse power flow and an increased demand by uncontrollable EV charging, and (iii) network asymmetry due to unbalanced PV generation and EV charging demand. To address these challenges and to facilitate the energy transition, DSOs need to invest the necessary resources to modernize the LVDG through advanced control strategies.

In this context, this paper also reviewed solutions available in the literature to address the aforementioned challenges. Selected solutions were applied to representative test feeders to assess and compare their impact on the LVDG operation. The study examined the use of OLTC transformers for voltage management in LVDGs, finding that while OLTCs transformers are effective, their high implementation cost necessitates a targeted deployment. Reactive power control by smart inverters is a widely adopted solution for voltage management. However, it is shown that several local-based methods can be inefficient and can unnecessarily increase the system loading and the grid losses compared to more complex centralized approaches. To reduce reverse power flow, prevent over-generation conditions, and provide an effective voltage management, PV curtailment is a well-known solution. However, PV curtailments introduces concerns regarding fairness and creates uncertainty about the economic viability of PV investments. A promising technology to enhance and optimize grid operations is the deployment of energy storage systems. This technology can aid in active power control by reducing congestion, reverse power flow, and peak loads, it can reduce the electricity cost of end-users, as well as provide voltage support. However, realizing their full potential for benefiting the grid operation through cost-effective local-based schemes is proven challenging. Similarly, smart and coordinated EV charging with the capability to provide V2G applications, can improve the grid operation and enable higher EV penetration before requiring expensive infrastructure upgrades. This requires subsidies and the creation of revenue streams to incentivize EV owners to participate, given the potential negative impact on the vehicles batteries. For network symmetrization and the reduction of VUF and CUF, wired solutions, such as phase selectors, and non-wired solutions with the use of phase balancing three-phase four-wire inverters are commonly considered.

All simulation models used in this paper have been made publicly available through an open repository¹ to support relevant research activities.

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to acknowledge the support from the Electricity Authority of Cyprus for providing field measurements and grid information regarding the test feeders used in this work.

This work is supported in part by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101172819 (CABLEGNOSIS); in part by the Republic of Cyprus and the Cyprus Research and Innovation Foundation under grant agreement CODEVELOP-REPowerEU/1223/0091 (GridGnosis), through the European Union’s NextGenerationEU initiative and the Recovery and Resilience Plan of Cyprus (Cyprus - Tomorrow); and in part by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739551 (KIOS CoE - TEAMING) and from the Republic of Cyprus through the Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digital Policy.

Appendix A - Representative LV Feeders

There are two main design layouts for LVDGs with distinct differences between them. The first design layout, which is used extensively in Europe, forms a radial three-phase four-wire network with a 230 V phase-neutral and a 400 V line-to-line nominal voltage. In addition, a European style LVDG can supply with power a large number of consumers with either a single-phase or a three-phase connection. In the second design layout, which is used extensively in North America, the LVDG is supplied by a centre-tapped single-phase transformer with a 120 V phase-neutral and a 240 V line-to-line nominal voltage. Due to the lower voltage rating and transformer configuration, a North American style LVDG supplies with power a lower number of only single-phase connected consumers. In addition, several countries have adopted LVDGs that are a combination of the European and North American layouts. This work focuses on European style LVDGs since the European design is the most widely adopted [163]. Nonetheless, the key challenges related to a high PV and EV penetration and the impact of most solutions presented in this paper are also extendable to North American style networks

Figure A.1 illustrates the single line diagram of the developed representative low voltage feeders. These test systems have been developed with the aid of the Electricity Authority of Cyprus by analysing several real LV feeders from the power system of Cyprus. Their RMS phasor simulation models are publicly available in both MATLAB/Simulink and the open access software OpenDSS. A brief description of the characteristics of each representative test system is given below while a summary of their key characteristics is given in Table A.I.

A.1. Urban Feeder

The urban feeder is characterized by a high energy consumption density, relatively short line lengths, a ground mounted distribution transformer with several outgoing laterals, and a supply of energy to customers through underground cables. Its load mixture typically consists of residential apartment complexes, commercial/retail stores, and offices. The urban feeder illustrated in Fig. A.1(a) has 3 outgoing laterals servicing in total 12 apartment complexes (10 individual supply

Representative Low Voltage Distribution Grids

Figure A.1: Single line diagram of the three representative low voltage feeders.

points for each apartment complex) and 7 commercial/retail stores. The overall underground cable length in this feeder is 1.125 km with a highest end-of-feeder distance of 0.265 km.

A.2. Sub-Urban Feeder

A representative sub-urban feeder is illustrated in Fig. A.1(b). The distribution transformer in sub-urban systems can either be ground mounted or pole mounted depending on the required capacity. While the load mixture of the considered feeder is pure residential it is common to have sub-urban systems with varying percentages of load mixtures with commercial/retail stores. In total there are 50 residential consumers, of which 10 have a three-phase connection. The total line length is 1.24 km while the highest end-of-feeder distance is approximately 0.5 km. The supply of energy in the sub-urban feeder is achieved mainly through overhead distribution lines.

A.3. Rural Feeder

Due to a low population/energy density, a rural system is characterized by larger line lengths when compared to the other types of LV feeders. Typically, the supply of energy from a pole mounted distribution transformer to the consumers is achieved through overhead lines. The load mixture of these feeders is mainly residential. Figure A.1(c) illustrates the representative rural feeder with 20 consumers of which 5 are three-phase connected. The total length of the distribution lines is 1.81 km with an end-of-feeder distance of 0.94 km.

Table A.I: Characteristics of Representative LV Feeders

Feeder	Overall Length (km)	Highest EoF Dist. (km)	Number of Loads	Avg. Grid Imp. (Ω/km)
Urban	1.12	0.26	127	0.22+j0.75
Sub-urban	1.24	0.50	50	0.74+j0.79
Rural	1.81	0.94	20	0.59+j0.79

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